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The Challenges Of Senior Citizens In Nigeria: Urgent Need For Social Protection Interventions

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ABSTRACT

Senior citizenship itself is a gift of nature. Not every created human being will have the privilege to reach old age. Economic challenges affect the well-being of older persons globally and Nigeria in particular. Traditionally, Nigerians depend on their children in old age for their well-being. Governments at all levels often introduce policies to provide for the aged but ignore their implementations. Pensioners among them find it difficult to receive their pensions regularly. There are multiple challenges confronting the elderly people in Nigeria which include poverty, physiological problems, elderly abuse, housing, ill health, loneliness, and isolation. There are many chronic diseases suffered by the elderly people. The introduction of a Social Protection Policy on the welfare of the elderly persons would help to reduce the suffering of senior citizens. The necessity of encouraging, orientating, creating awareness and sensitizing all stakeholders like the governments, institutions, organizations, civil society groups, private sector, community leaders, youth groups, health-care providers, philanthropists, families members, and the general public etc, towards helping the senior citizens is sacrosanct. The researchers adopted activity theory which focuses on the person and the psyche in adapting and adjusting to changes associated with growing old. The research method adopted for this work is wholly content analysis through secondary data from scholars' literatures, articles, journals, and books including the Act establishing the National Senior Citizens Centre, 2017, which formed the sources of information for this research. The study which is meant to identify, analyze, and find solutions to the problems of the senior citizens, discovered that the aging in human experiences imposes innumerable challenges or problems, with economic problems or poverty as major. It recommends that health care services should be based on the felt needs of the elderly population, as well as the education, training, and information needs, while the Nigerian government should introduce policy frameworks that would ensure that the older persons in Nigeria enjoy social security and protection.

Keywords: Social Protection, Senior Citizens, Health Challenges, Poverty

INTRODUCTION

The Federal Government recently cautioned against stigmatising and discriminating against senior citizens and the ageing population in Nigeria. The pioneer Director General of the National Senior Citizens Centre, Dr Emem Omokaro, gave the warning in her keynote address at the Humanitarian Service Diamond Awards 2024 held in Abuja recently. The DG emphasised that it was important to address the growing perception, especially by the younger generation, that ageing parents are a 'distraction and burden' to the larger society.

Her statement was also a reaction to reports that the ageing population is not covered by the health insurance scheme just as some banks in Nigeria have it as a policy not to grant loan facilities above

certain amounts to people who are advanced in age. The interesting thing is that, traditionally, because of norms of reciprocity, everybody assumes that family is there to care; adult children will do the needful and they (the older citizens) will be covered through their benevolence. According Singh (2001) in Paswan, et.al (2005), the aged are not a spent force, they are a treasure house of knowledge. They are not to be sidelined; they are to be mainstreamed. These flowers may be faded but they still smell sweet through empowerment.

One of the bills that former President Muhammadu Buhari did not sign into law is the Older Persons (Rights and Privileges) Bill. The bill had been passed by both chambers of the National Assembly in 2021 but did not receive presidential assent. There is a lot of focus on Nigeria's teeming youthful population with admonitions to the country to unlock the genius of its human capital. The aging portion of the population mostly seems ignored in policy development and implementation. Although sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) has a smaller proportion of the aged in its population compared to developed regions, it is projected that this segment of the population would grow over the coming years. According to statistics from the National Population Commission, the population of older persons in Nigeria rose from about 4.6 million in 1991 to 6.9 million in 2006. This population is projected to reach almost 28 million by 2050.

Care for the aged in Nigeria and in other parts of the SSA region has mostly been carried out by the traditional family and other informal support systems. The absence of publicly funded social security systems in the region makes this segment of the population even more vulnerable.

However, the Nigerian population demographics have been changing, arising from rural-to-urban migration within the country and the increasing numbers of the 'youthful' population emigrating to other countries. Given these trends, the traditional family support systems for the aging population are fast disappearing. This presents increasing challenges in meeting the economic, healthcare, and social needs of the aging population.

High level of poverty, which is driven by equally high unemployment rate, is one of Nigeria's major challenges. As such, one can reasonably expect that the aged, who have either retired from formal work or are less productive, are quite vulnerable to economic shocks. The impacts of the helplessness include fast deteriorating health due to lack of access to quality healthcare, recourse to working after formal retirement, and social isolation. The aged group tends to need more healthcare services. In the circumstance of Nigeria's deteriorating socioeconomic and healthcare conditions, access to quality healthcare – especially geriatric care – by this demographic has become even more limited.

Under Section 16(2) (d) of the 1999 Constitution (as amended), state policy is mandated at ensuring "that suitable and adequate shelter, suitable and adequate food, reasonable national minimum living wage, old age care and pensions, and unemployment, sick benefits and welfare of the disabled are provided for all citizens". Nigeria has signed both regional and international instruments relating to care of its aged population, including the African Union (AU) Policy Framework and Plan of Action on Ageing, and the United Nations (UN) International Plan of Action on Ageing, which was adopted by the General Assembly in December 1991. Under the UN plan, member states are encouraged to develop and integrate policies for ensuring that older persons have access to adequate food, water, shelter, clothing and healthcare; opportunity to work or other income-generating opportunities; autonomy over withdrawal from the labour force; appropriate educational and training programmes; safe, effective and preferred environments; continued social integration and participation in social and communal life including access to the educational, cultural, spiritual and recreational resources of society; continued protection of their rights to freedom of associations; family and communal care; institutional health, social and legal care; protection of their fundamental rights while residing in shelters or similar facilities; security; and equal and fair treatment.

Nigeria enacted the National Senior Citizens Centre Act 2017, which established the National Senior Citizens Centre (NSCC), headquartered in Abuja. The objective of the centre is to identify the different needs of the aging population and develop and implement programmes and schemes to address these needs. Unsurprisingly, however, the NSCC has not been delivering its objectives. Not much was done in implementing the legislative enactment until 2021 when former President Buhari approved a N2.5 billion take-off grant for it.

The Older Persons (Rights and Privileges) Bill is a more holistic legislation that provides for the rights and privileges of older persons, in terms of healthcare, housing, economic benefits, and adequate standard of living. The bill provides for the rights of older persons to freedom from

discrimination; to express their wishes and preferences regarding future health and long-term care-related decisions and to have those expressions respected; to social protection, including income security without discrimination on the basis of age, gender, or health status; and equality. The bill expressly provides for the inclusion of older persons in every national programme on income generation of the state or federal government. Many countries of the world, the older persons were seen to have not been opportune to enjoy a decent status in society, especially in developing countries, which are economically poor, subjected to the ravage of demographic transition, migration, modernization, dwindling joint family, market economy, poor public health and hygiene and low social and economic security (Paswan, et.al, 2005). They further narrated the urgent need to empower the elderly through implementation of mass action programmes that are multi-prolonged. Empowering the elderly consist of enabling them in at least three spheres or dimensions of life, such as economic, social, and health, which are critical to empowerment and integration, enabling the elderly to effectively negotiate and procure their needs and function as a useful citizen (Paswan, et.al, 2005).

The bill also makes significant provisions for public healthcare services for older persons. The proposed law makes it mandatory for public hospitals to establish geriatric wards for the exclusive use of older persons. Even where the wards are used for other purposes in emergency situations, they will be reverted exclusively for geriatric use thereafter. The bill also provides that primary healthcare centres will be modified to serve the geriatric population and further makes provisions for mobile “hospital on wheel” healthcare facilities to serve physically challenged older persons.

While the reputation of the public healthcare system in Nigeria is poor, implementation of these provisions in public hospitals will alleviate some of the challenges our older people are facing, especially in rural areas where the lack of formal healthcare is more pronounced. The creation of the ‘specialised’ wards and services will also encourage development of skills and investment in that area of healthcare. The bill expressly provides that the federal and state Ministries of Health shall train community-based health workers among older persons and health personnel to specialise in the geriatric care and health problems of older persons. The government is also to provide an enabling environment for private institutions to train same as approved by the Federal Ministry of Health. Furthermore, the government is to encourage and create an enabling environment for the establishment of day care centres, nursing/respite homes, and hospices throughout the country, which shall be approved by the relevant government agencies.

In addition to these provisions, the Older Persons (Rights and Privileges) Bill also makes provisions for health insurance and costs. It expressly states that the National Health Insurance Scheme shall cover all indigent older persons, and that the NHIS shall design insurance product for coverage of the elderly with sustainable funding options. It further states that older persons shall be entitled to the grant of 50 percent discount and exemption from VAT on medical and dental services, pharmaceutical services, diagnostic and laboratory fees in all private hospitals, medical facilities, outpatient clinic, and home healthcare services, as determined by the NHIS.

The bill also provides for the provisions of social safety assistance for older persons during disasters, calamities, or economic shocks. The assistance includes food, medicines, house repairs, and they are to be sourced from National Emergency Management Agency (NEMA)/State Emergency Management Agency (SEMA)/Local Government Emergency Management Agency (LGEMA) and the National Commission for Refugees and Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs).

Regarding economic protection for the older persons, the bill provides for the monthly payment of a stipend amounting to not less than 50 percent of the national minimum wage, subject to the review every five years by the National Assembly, to every indigent older person. This payment is the responsibility of the social welfare units of local governments. The bill also makes provisions for some rebates for older persons such as 50 percent of actual fare for all modes of transportation; utilities such as electricity, water, telephone; and fees charged by theatres, cinema houses, and other leisure houses.

Government at all levels are also expected to protect this group of persons from victimization and vulnerability through provision of Social Protection Policies. This Social Protection will save them and enable them to fill belonged into the society after they were no longer active.

According to Garcia and Gruat (2003), the existence of social protection can be recognized as one of the most significant social achievements of the 20th century. Systems of social protection enable societies to advance the well-being and security of their citizens by protecting them from vulnerability and deprivation so that they can live a decent life. On the one hand, social protection can meet the essential needs of human survival by ensuring that all men and women have basic social and economic security. They further emphasized that it can play a more far-reaching role in enhancing the quality of life of individuals and societies by developing and unleashing human potential, facilitating structural change, increasing stability, advancing social justice and cohesion, and promoting economic dynamism.

This research is focused on the impact of social protection policies on the lives of the elderly citizens known as Senior citizens in Nigeria and how they can be reached, protected from victimization and vulnerability. The work also covers the following aspects; challenges or problems of the Elderly, diseases and other health related challenges of elderly people, National senior citizens establishment act, differences between urban and rural settings approaches to maintenance of elderly people. It ended with recommendation on how the suffering of the elderly persons would be reduced.

LITERATURE REVIEW:

SENIOR CITIZENS AND SOCIAL PROTECTION

Senior Citizens

Senior citizens in the actual sense are referred to people who have reached certain chronicle age. Many scholars and various countries have different views on the age range that can form or be classified as senior citizens. Elderly or old age consists of ages nearing or surpassing the average life span of human beings. The boundary of old age cannot be defined exactly because it does not have the same meaning in all societies. Abeykon and Ruwanthi (2008) considered people above 60 years of age as old. Siddhisena, 2004 in Ayoob, 2020 stated that Sri Lanka also regards 60 and above as the demarcation age in identifying the elderly population. World health Organization categorized people who are of 60 years and above as the elderly or aged, while United States of America refers to those who are 65 years and above as aged. India age limit for the elderly varies from 55 years to 65 years (Ayoob, 2020). Government of India had adopted National Policy on Older Persons in January, 1999, which defined the senior citizen or elderly as a person who is of age 60 years or above. The United Nations agreed cutoff is 60 years and above, and this appears acceptable in the African setting including Nigeria, as the retirement age of majority of civil servants in Nigeria hovers around this age (Daramola et. al (N.D). Nigeria recently during the reign of President Goodluck Jonathan, has increased the retirement age of certain groups in civil service like in the tertiary institutions to 65 and 70 for all other staff and professors, respectively.

Cited from the Reference Note of Lok Sabha Secretariat, the Parliament Library and Reference, Research, Documentation and Information Services (LARRDIS, 2013), the United Nations adopted the 1st International Plan of Action on Ageing in Vienna in 1982, and it took until 1991 for the General Assembly to adopt the UN Principles for Older Persons (Resolution 46/91) and its 5 main themes - independence, participation, care, self-fulfillment and dignity. In 1999, with the International Year of Older Persons, came the Conceptual Framework based on the Plan and Principles with 4 priority areas (i) the situation of older persons, (ii) individual life long development, (iii) the relationship between generations, (iv) the inter-relationship of population, aging and development. Finally, in Madrid in 2002, the 2nd World Assembly on Ageing (WAA) had adopted unanimously a Political Declaration and an International Strategic Plan of Action on Ageing. The 2004 report of the Secretary-General to the General Assembly recommends "to assign fulltime focal points on ageing and provide them with adequate resources to further implementation." The International day of older persons is celebrated every year on 1 October [SeniorCitizensProblemsandWelfare.pdf](#).

Senior citizens suffer from depression, they lose their social status and become economically poor, as well as suffer from economic and health problems (Guruswamy, 2001; Ramamurti, 2003). Dharmalingam and Murugan (2001) reports that elderly widows become the victims of neglects and discrimination on account of gender, age and widowhood.

Overview of Social Protection and Types

Social protection is known to be the set of policies and programs designed to reduce poverty and vulnerability by promoting efficient labor markets, diminishing people's exposure to risks, and enhancing their capacity to protect themselves against hazards, social risks, such as unemployment, exclusion, sickness, disability, and old age (World Bank, 2001).

The United Nations Research Institute for Social Development defined Social protection as policies concerned with preventing, managing, and overcoming situations that adversely affect people's well-being (UNRISD, 2010). Social protection schemes are very significant options to reduce poverty and inequality. The Schemes contribute to economic growth by raising labour productivity and enhancing social stability, and not only restricted to helping to prevent individuals and families from falling and remaining in abject poverty. Social Protection can be viewed as when resources, either cash or in-kind, are transferred to vulnerable individuals or households with no other means of adequate support, including single parents, the homeless, the aged or the physically or mentally challenged (Howell, 2001). Social protection plays a key role in realizing the rights of persons with disabilities of all ages: providing them with an adequate standard of living, a basic level of income security; thus reducing levels of poverty and vulnerability.

Social protection as an approach, is being directed to reduction of risk and vulnerabilities, interventions from private, public as well as voluntary organisations. It also designed supports to assist higher percentage of households in their struggle to overcome hazards, reduce and prevent impacts of vulnerabilities that affect wellbeing, consumption and investments. UNICEF is a leading global partner on social protection, which her impacts can be seen in more than 150 countries of the world, delivering social assistance – from cash transfer programmes to social welfare services – that addresses child poverty in all its dimensions. Other examples of Social Protection interventions in Nigeria which extended to all states in Nigeria are; Family Economic Advancement Programme, Better Life for Rural Women, Directorate for Food, Roads & Rural Infrastructure; National Directorate of Employment; and Family Support Programme.

The Social Protection in Nigeria has constitutional backup that can be traced down to 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, Section 17 (subsection 3) captured in Ikeanyibe (2013, pg 258) as in the following:

That the State shall direct its policy towards ensuring that;

- a. all citizens without discrimination on any group whatsoever, have the opportunity for securing adequate means of livelihood as well as adequate opportunity to secure suitable employment;
- b. the conditions for work are just and humane, and that there are adequate facilities for leisure and for social, religious and cultural life;
- c. the health, safety and welfare of all persons in employment are safeguarded and not endangered or abused;
- d. that there are adequate medical and health facilities for all persons;
- e. there is equal work for equal pay without discrimination on account of sex, or any other ground whatsoever;
- f. children, young persons and the aged are protected against any exploitation whatsoever, and against moral and material neglect;
- g. provision is made for public assistance in deserving cases or other conditions of need, and
- h. the evolution and promotion of family life is encouraged (Constitution, 1999, 17(3)).

Similar provision of Social Protection Policy was made in Education, 1999 Constitution (Section 18 (1&3) in Ikeanyibe (2013, p. 258), where Government policy in education should be directed towards ensuring that there are equal and adequate educational opportunities at all levels, striving to eradicate illiteracy by providing free, compulsory and universal primary education; free secondary education; free university education and free adult literacy programme (Constitution, Section 18 (1&3)).

The challenges facing the elderly in Nigeria including many other developing nations may be due to weak or nonexistent social security policies for older persons (Aiyede, 2015). According to Magnus Eze (2011), the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria dwells on the Fundamental Objectives and Directive Principles of State Policy; particularly S.14 (20) (b) which provides that;

“the security and welfare of the people shall be the primary purpose of the government.” S.16 (2) (d) insists “that suitable and adequate shelter and food, reasonable minimum living wage, old age care and pensions and unemployment, sick benefits and welfare of the disabled are provided for all citizens. Though, care for the elderly has not been of priority to successive governments in Nigeria.

A Bill sponsored by Senator Ganiyu Solomon of an opposition party, the Action Congress of Nigeria (Lagos State), was passed on July 14, 2009 by the 6th Senate of Nigeria for “An Act to Establish a National Centre for Elderly Persons for General Purpose of providing Welfare and Recreational Facilities for the Elderly and the Designing of Developmental Programmes and Activities for the Advancement of Elderly Persons in Nigeria (Magnus Eze, 2011).” In June 2010, there was another bill sponsored by Senator Anyim Ude of the ruling People’s Democratic Party (Ebonyi State) for “An Act to provide Social Security for Unemployed Graduates and the Aged in Nigeria and for Purposes connected Thereto.”

National Senior Citizens Centre Act, 2017

The Act to establish the National Senior Citizens Centre in the country to cater for the needs of the Senior citizens and for related matters was enacted in 2017 by the National Assembly of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (NSCCA, 2017). In this research, the Act details were analyzed and summarized in parts and sections to enable it convey a comprehensive expatiation to the understanding of the common man.

Part 1: This contains the Declaration of Policy, Establishment and composition of the National Senior Citizens Centre Governing Board with emphasis and strength drawn from the 1999 Constitution of Nigeria, which states in section 16 (2) (d), ‘that there shall be a State Policy to provide adequate Social Services and an improved quality of life for the elderly’.

It has all the characteristics of an Act, which shall be a body corporate with perpetual succession and may sue and be sued in its corporate name with its National headquarters at the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja. The Act approved any state in the federation that desires, to establish a Senior Citizens Centre in such state. The Management of the National Centre will have a Governing Board with a Chairman, ten (10) members and the Director-General of the Centre, who are persons with proven integrity and as well appointees of the President. The members of the Board shall hold office for a term of four years in the first instance and may be eligible for reappointment for another term of four years and no more. A member also may cease to hold office on the conditions of unsound mind; bankruptcy; convicted of a felony or offence of dishonesty; guilty of serious misconduct in relation to his duties or vote of no confidence by Mr. President.

Part II: This part elaborates the functions of the National Senior Citizens Centre. It identifies the needs, trainings, and opportunities of senior citizens in the country and be responsible for the provision of recreational, sports, educational, health and social programs and facilities designed for the full enjoyment and benefit of the senior citizens in the country as well as provide guidance and counselling for them. It also has the function of initiating, developing and implementing productive activities and work schemes for senior citizens in order to provide income or otherwise supplement their earnings; as well maintain and promote links with state and local government for provision of facilities, professional advice services and trainings.

National Senior Citizens Centre Establishing Act has in parts III, IV, V, many other provisions like staffing, financial provisions, supplementary provisions relating to the Council that needed to be known but could not be presented in this research because of space but contained in the Act establishing the National Senior Citizens Centre. This Act is certified in accordance with section 2 (1) of the Acts Authentication Act Cap. A2, Laws of the Federation of Nigeria 2004 as true copy of this Bill by the Clerk of the National Assembly, Mohammed AtabaSani-Omolori on 27th day of December, 2017 and signed into law by General Muhammadu Buhari, GCF, President of the Federal Republic of Nigeria on 24th day of January, 2018 [National-Senior-Citizens-Centre-Act-2017.pdf \(placng.org\)](#). The National Senior Citizens Centre is domiciled in the Federal Ministry of Humanitarian Affairs, Disaster Management and Social Development.

The following is the list of the some of the best elderly care homes in Nigeria:

Holy Family Home for the Elderly – Regina Mundi; Rockgarden Homecare Agency; Wellcare Home Medicals Limited; Family Ark Mission International; Alpha Nursing Home; Winiseph Care Home;

Rhoda Home Care; Blue Gate Home Care Health Care Agency; Greymate Care; and Elderly Care Home.

Types of Social Protection Policies & Programmes

Specifically, there are four main social protection policies and programmes known to scholars especially in Nigeria. They are thematically discussed below:

Protective Social Assistance:

These are skills or programmes of government, established to assist the ageing population e.g. Pension Scheme, because government knew that as a public servant, one day, you will exit from the system, therefore, try to remember them at the old age through the Pension Scheme. In Nigeria, this scheme is abused because many falsified their age in order to stay a long period in the service unlike Western world where Civil or public servants will apply for resignation. Federal civil servants clamoured for retirement age elongation and was successfully adopted into 65 years retirement age. Nigeria Professors have been approved of 70 years while Judges are still proposing for 75 years of retirement.

Preventive Social Protection Policies:

This preventive social protection policy is but not the only approach to poverty reduction but in combination with other approaches like; provision of social and economic services, infrastructure development, and institutional development. Preventive social protection approach can make a strong contribution, alongside other approaches, in the areas of controlling and avoiding the slide into poverty and with its recovery assistance. It is designed by government to avert poverty, as well as measures to safeguard the health of the citizens (e.g. School feeding programme) which is still ongoing in Nigeria. Long-term programmes for annihilation of poverty can be the best option for chronically pulverised vulnerable groups and their lineage to escape poverty.

Promotional Income Social Protection Policy:

This is policies designed to enhance activities such as life skills, occasional and agricultural training for the youths as well as increase in access to credit through Micro opportunities. Such programmes include in-kind and in-cash transfers, and food for work initiatives. Cash transfers are a means of financially supporting the most vulnerable households to improve the child's access to essential goods and services, such as health and education. They include the use of child support grants, child and family allowances and targeted and conditional cash transfers. They may be combined with investment in child education and health services, and redistributive tax policies. In-kind transfers provide access to essential goods and services instead of cash payments.

Transformative Social Protection Policy: This Policy was designed to address social inequality and exclusion through awareness campaign, stigma reduction campaign and policy dialogues to protect the down trodden in our midst e.g. protection of inheritance right, like NOA – National Orientation Agency, NOC – National Orientational Campaign.

Social Assistance Programmes and policies targeted those in most need, and provide sustainable support. Economic policies, which included social assistance, and household economic strengthening, require substantial research, monitoring, and gatekeeping to ensure that the poorest and most vulnerable are reached and that long-term benefits can be achieved for families, including child headed households (Zaitov, et al, 2021).

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

There are three major theories of the aging individual; **disengagement theory, activity theory, and continuity theory**. Each focus on the individual person and the psyche in adapting and adjusting to changes associated with growing old. For sake of clarity and the closer connection to the aim of the research, the activity theory was adopted. Gerontologist Robert J. Havighurst developed the activity theory of aging in 1961. This is based on the idea that older people who are active are more satisfied with their lives than those who are not. Havighurst originally framed the theory as a response to disengagement theory, which is described in more detail below.

Tenets of the Theory

- i. As people age, their social roles change. For example, when a person retires, he/she is no longer in the social role of employee or breadwinner. When children grow up and move out, the aging parent is no longer in the role of caregiver.

- ii. The activity theory of aging proposes that older adults can continue the level of activity and social interaction that they enjoyed in middle age by replacing their former roles with new ones. For example, the role of employee can be replaced with the role of volunteer. According to activity theory, changing roles and remaining active improves self-concept and adjustment to growing older.
- iii. The chief criticism of activity theory is that not all older people can remain active. Barriers to remaining active in old age include physical and mental health issues as well as social restraints such as poverty or class.
- iv. Another criticism is that some older people have no desire to engage in new roles and activities.

Application of the Theory in the Study

One of the tenets of the activity theory states that old age has significant impact on the social roles of the older people thereby making their social roles as employees or breadwinners reduced. When children grow up and move out, the aging parents are no longer in the role of caregivers. In the study, community leaders, children and family members of the older persons should not neglect them at the old age but give them support since they could not provide for themselves, as it was also observed that those retired from employed jobs, sometimes gratuities or pensions are difficult to be accessed at when most needed.

Another tenet of the activity theory proposes that older adults can continue the level of activity and social interaction that they enjoyed in middle age by replacing their former roles with new ones which will improve self-concept and adjustment to growing older. For example, the role of employees can be replaced with the role of volunteers. The establishment of the national senior citizens centre or older people's homes in this research provided the new or alternative to the foregone activities of the older persons, which would make them to regain their pro-activeness to enable them age gracefully.

The criticisms and barriers to the tenets of the activity theory make some of the old people to remain or choose not to remain active at the old age. Some of the barriers include physical and mental health issues, social restraints such as poverty or class as well as, in some case, no desire to engage in new roles and activities. In this research, the introduction of Social Protection Policy on the welfare of the elderly persons would help to reduce the suffering of the senior citizens mostly the sick ones. All stakeholders like the governments, institutions, organizations, civil society groups, private sector, community leaders, youth groups, health-care providers, philanthropists, families' members, and the general public etc, should be encouraged towards helping the senior citizens. Nigerian government should introduce practical policy frameworks that would ensure that the older persons in Nigeria enjoy social security, good health and protection.

RESEARCH METHOD

The research method adopted for this work is wholly content analysis through secondary data. Other scholars' literatures, articles, journal and books including the Act establishing National Senior Citizens Centre, 2017 were also consulted, which formed the sources of information for this research.

CHALLENGES OF THE ELDERLY PEOPLE IN NIGERIA

Conceptually, pensions are defined as the remuneration due to a retired civil, public (servant) or cooperate individual employees after meritorious services to his/her employers over a defined period. While in the services of an organisation (private or public) an employee is entitled to salaries as agreed in the employment contract and duly communicated. This and associated benefits constitute his income from employment. Upon retirement, he no longer earns such salaries. What becomes his income is now pensions payable monthly. Initially the burden of pensions payment is upon his former employer as provided by law (Employee Compensation Act, 2010).

However due to inherent limitations and poor administration of pensions resulting to avoidable delays and to a reasonable extent; none payments, accumulated backlog, frustrations and associated pains on the pensioners (beneficiaries), there was need for a review. This resulted to the current pensions act which gave rise to the emergence of current Pension Fund Administrators (PFAs). PFAs are government appointed/ approved companies engaged in pensions fund administration.

While in service, the employee contributes eight per cent and his employer contributes ten per cent of the employee's monthly income to the pension fund. The employee's contribution goes to the dedicated fund managed by his choice PFA while the employer also transfers same to the PFA.

The accumulated contribution is used to pay pensions over a period to the pensioner upon retirement. This payment arrangement could be under Annuity or programmed withdrawal as the pensioner may agree to.

The act further provides that the pensioner is given a bulk payment of at least 25 per cent% of his accumulated contribution while the balance is spread for monthly pensions payment to the pensioner. Irrespective of this noble legislation, Pensioners in Nigeria face many challenges, including:

- These PFAs are business entities only interested in profit maximisation at the detriment of the welfare of the pensioners.
- Pensioners are sweet – tongued into signing PFA agreements which they least understand, hence regret same after entering into such unexplained agreements.
- Accumulated contributions are savings/ investments by a pensioner and the pensioner deserves to access same as at when needed to solve maturing personal obligations.
- Pensioners are older and elderly people whose maintenance and medical bills are huge, hence the need to remove all restrictions affecting their access to accumulated savings in their PFA accounts.
- Monthly pensions payable is only as agreed and meagre;
- They are not susceptible to interest rate changes especially on an inflationary economic situation like the Nigerian experience.
- Even where interest rate adjustments are made, Pensioners only receive what is given by the PFAs without any choice. Who do you complain to?
- Communication and engagement with the pensioner cases immediately after taking in the pensioner's accumulated contributions, the pensioner is henceforth 'on his own'.
- The pensioner suffers financial difficulties and unable to access his accumulated savings domiciled in the PFA account and sometimes dies while the PFA smiles to the bank consistently with huge interest income earned from the pensioners funds.

SOME DISEASES ENCOUNTERED BY THE SENIOR CITIZENS (ELDERLY)

Life longevity and good health in human context, can be tagged as one of the man's greatest achievements. Factors like improved nutrition, sanitation, advanced medical facilities, health care, education and economic well-being attribute to people's live longevity. The social and economic implications of ageing are profound, extending far beyond the individual older person and the immediate family, touching broader society and the entire community in unprecedented ways. Irrespective that older people are a precious, often ignored resource that assist through their important contribution to the fabric of our societies. Ageing has social, economic and cultural challenges to individuals, families, societies and the global community as well ([Scheme for Senior Citizens - Final.pdf](#) (ssepd.gov.in)). The ageing is a stage of life in human existence, which the people who have grown old, experience innumerable health problems as detailed below.

Old age is inevitable to chronic diseases but most often, some can be preventable. Medical conditions have become a more common feature of older life. It's important for us all to understand the most common medical conditions so that we can spot the symptoms. The following are some of the major sicknesses of the elderly persons:

1. Arthritis: Arthritis is one of the most common medical conditions among older people that causes joint pain and inflammation, which can restrict your movement. There are two common types of arthritis: osteoarthritis (caused by wear and tear because the older we are, the more we have used our joints) and rheumatoid arthritis (is an autoimmune disease, where the immune system attacks the lining of the joints). Symptoms of arthritis include; Joint pain, tenderness and stiffness; Restricted movement; and Inflammation in and around the joints.

2. Blindness: The blindness is mostly caused by age-related macular degeneration (AMD), which occurs when deposits build up on the macula (a small area at the centre of the retina). AMD can also be caused by abnormal blood vessels developing under the macula. Other medical conditions— such as glaucoma, cataract and diabetes etc, can cause sight loss too.

3. Parkinson's Disease: Parkinson's disease is a chronic and progressive condition that damages certain parts of the brain. The main cause of Parkinson's is a loss of nerve cells in a part of the brain called the substantianigra. This leads to a reduction in dopamine, an important chemical in the brain. Symptoms; Involuntary shaking of particular parts of the body (tremor), Slow movement and Stiff and

inflexible muscles. Currently, there is no cure for Parkinson's disease but, there are treatments available that can reduce the symptoms.

4. Stroke: A stroke occurs when the blood supply to a part of your brain is cut off. Strokes are particularly common among older people in the average age of 74, though sometimes, younger ages can develop stroke. Without blood, brain cells can be damaged and may even die. Having a stroke can be life-threatening if you don't seek medical attention straight away. Face dropped or fallen on one side; arms shrink and unable to be raised and loss of speech are the symptoms.

5. Chronic Kidney Disease: Other medical conditions that can affect the kidneys and lead to chronic kidney disease are; kidney infections, high blood pressure, diabetes and kidney inflammation. Symptoms are; Shortness of breath, Feeling sick, Blood in your urine, Swollen ankles, feet or hands and Tiredness.

6. Coronary Heart Disease: Coronary heart disease (CHD) happens when fatty substances build up in the arteries, blocking the blood supply to the heart. Symptoms: are; angina, heart attacks and heart failure. While the risk factors include: Smoking, High cholesterol, High blood pressure, Diabetes, Obesity.

7. Dementia: Dementia is a progressive disorder that affects memory and overall brain function, which is relatively common in older people within 65 to 80 years of age and above. The most common and well-known form of dementia is Alzheimer's disease. Vascular dementia is another type of dementia that develops as a result of a stroke or blood vessel deterioration. Symptoms: Difficulty remembering recent events or forgetting date and where you are; Problems in conversation – struggling to follow along or to find the right words; Difficulty judging distance.

8. Diabetes: Diabetes is a lifelong condition, which occurs when the body doesn't have enough insulin. This could be because the pancreas isn't producing enough, or because the body is resistant to the insulin it produces. There are two (2) types of diabetes; Type 1 and Type 2.

Type 1 diabetes is an autoimmune condition, where the body attacks the cells that produce insulin. Type 2 diabetes, on the other hand, is when the body does not produce enough insulin or the insulin it makes doesn't work properly. Type 2 can be prevented through healthy eating, maintaining weight, and regular exercise.

9. High Cholesterol: Cholesterol is a fatty substance that is created by your liver and is also found in some foods. Lipoproteins in the blood carry cholesterol around the body, which also has two types; low density and high density. Lifestyles that lead to high cholesterol are smoking, unhealthy diet, diabetes, high blood pressure, family history of stroke and, Age, all which can be managed through exercises, healthy diet, reduce alcohol intake and quit on smoking.

Other Chronic diseases of the elderly persons which could not be discussed because of space but are worthy of note are; Hypertension (Blood pressure); Asthma; Cancer; Motor Neurone Disease; Epilepsy; Chronic bronchitis; Deep vein thrombosis; Multiple Sclerosis; Osteoporosis; Paget's Disease of Bone; and Shingles.

OTHER PROBLEMS THE ELDERLY GROUP FACE

- **Economic Problems:** Economic problems are very basic to all the other problems the elderly faced which poverty is the climax, due to loss or reduction of earning power. When a person retired from the service, it results in loss of employment, social status and a substantial reduction in his income level. Majority of the elderly face acute financial problems and economically insecure. According to the Second World Assembly Record on Ageing (2018) cited in Daramola, et.al(N.D.), poverty among the elderly has been a global concern, as stipulated in the political declaration and Madrid International Plan of Action on Aging at the Second World Assembly on Ageing in April 2002. People in sub-Saharan Africa are among the poorest in the world, not only in terms of real income but also access to social services, (Khan, et. al, 2017 in Daramola et.al (N.D.). It was also discovered that the risk of poverty growing with older age is much higher among women than men (WHO, 2018). Daramola, et.al also cited the Second World Assembly on Ageing that poverty is a multidimensional issue with probable causes such as: personal factors; low income, unemployment, lack of education, lack of financial planning, social factors; lack of support from children/family or community, and government factors; poor pension programs, poor health systems including lack of health insurance, poor social protection and non-existent social security systems.

- **Physiological Problems:** Change is a constant factor, which human changes is inevitable. The elderly persons experience many physiological changes, which affects their psychology, behaviour as well as their attitudes, loss of physical strength and stamina. Many older persons have developed these challenges as a result of or most often over committed to duties and less concern to sport or unpressurized exercises that would strengthen their fitness. In the civil service, most workers indulge in sedentary works with less time for any other social activities, always being committed in office works or research.
- **Problem of Elder Abuse:** Elder abuse is usually defined as any ill treatment to an older person. It refers to “infliction of physical, emotional or psychological harm on an older adult”. Around 81 per cent of the elderly persons face the problem of verbal abuse, while 53 per cent of them face neglect followed by material abuse and 37 per cent on physical abuse [SeniorCitizensProblemsandWelfare.pdf](#). Elder abuse can also be viewed as a single or repeated act, or lack of appropriate action, occurring within any relationship where there is an expectation of trust, causing harm or distress to an older person (WHO, 2014). It has severe consequences including; physical and psychological trauma, pain, injury and even death. Elder abuse takes many forms including:
 - 1) Physical abuse i.e. hitting or shaking;
 - 2) sexual abuse i.e. rape and coerced nudity;
 - 3) psychological/emotional abuse i.e. verbal harassment or humiliation;
 - 4) abandonment, neglect or failure to provide adequate care; and
 - 5) financial abuse or exploitation.The impact of trauma may be worsened because of shame and fear, causing a reluctance to seek help, and it has been reported that victims of elder abuse are more likely die prematurely than people who are not (WHO, 2014 cited in Damarola et. al (N.D). Risk factors that may increase the potential for abuse of an older person can be identified at different levels and include: individual; poor physical and mental health of the victim, mental disorders and alcohol/substance abuse in the abuser etc., relationship; shared living situations, poor family relationships etc., community; social isolation of caregivers and older persons, and socio-cultural beliefs and practices (WHO, 2014; Ananias and Strydom, 2014; Chane and Adamek, 2015; Pillemer, et. al, 2016). Daramola, et.al. (N.D.) sighted that mass rural-urban migration of many young adults, made older parents in the rural areas be abandoned and neglected. The number of cases of elder abuse is projected to increase globally, as many countries have increasing population of older persons whose needs may not be fully met due to resource constraints, with the low and middle-income countries bearing more of the burden (WHO, 2014).
- **Housing related Problems:** Some children would abandon their elderly parents to suffer in abject tatted houses, isolation and loneliness, only to be taken into a well-furnished mansion in their lifeless bodies during their dead ceremonies. Housing for the aged should be suitable not only to the living pattern which they have established in optimum health, but also to conditions of failing health and illness, commonly associated with later years of life such as, failing eye sight, hearing, slowing and unsureness of step, diminishing energy and more acute disabilities, such as blindness, forgetfulness etc. The sizeable populations of older widows as well as the older males have been facing the problem of “where to live peacefully” (LARRDIS, 2013).
- **The Challenge of Finance:** The most health problems embattled by the elderly citizens are often created by no or little access to finance. There is need for increased utilization of affordable or accessible health services and taking a huge toll on the already dwindled finances of the older persons (Joshi, et.al. (2003). A significant percentage of older persons in Nigeria have huge financial burdens arising from greater healthcare needs and increased out-of-pocket health spending despite diminished incomes, with many unable to afford out-of-pocket payments for health costs, including prescription drugs (WHO, 2018). The limited financial capacity to absorb increasing medical bills is associated with severe consequences on access and utilization of health care and may result in financial catastrophe (Joshi, et.al., 2003; Tari, et.al, 2017 and HFF&H, 2013). Many governments introduced policies for the elderly healthcare provisions without implementations.
- **Problem of Loneliness and Isolation:** Loneliness and isolation have become important factors which lead to negative health outcomes and mental decline among the people, especially this condition severely influenced the senior citizens. The final stage in the life of elderly people is usually filled with isolation and loneliness (Ayoob, 2019 in Ayoob, 2020). Senior citizens who are isolated are more likely to need long term care as they age. The senior citizens in the study area mentioned that they engaged in some activities in order to tackle with their spare time. They overcome loneliness and

isolation by engaging in such activities with their children and grandchildren make them active and encourage them to play more roles and be active in the family, which made them healthier and reduce anxiety (Ayoob, 2020).

DIFFERENCES IN THE URBAN AND RURAL AREAS LIVELIHOOD OF THE SENIOR CITIZENS IN NIGERIA

A comparative analysis of the urban and rural areas as it affects the senior citizens, shows that the rural areas have been at a disadvantage with regards to opportunities, developments and prosperity.

Urban/Rural Divide: The urban/rural divide in access to needed services puts older people who have lived, worked and aged in rural areas at risk of experiencing the effects of accumulated disadvantage in their old age compared to those living in urban areas. Poverty is experienced in the rural areas with less business opportunities, poor or lack of infrastructures, urban migration, and disparities in the standard of living, access to essential services etc.

Health and Social Care: In Nigeria, there is an urban/rural difference in people's health and the social determinants of health. There are better access to fresh food, water, enjoy higher life expectancy, healthcare services and health infrastructure, loss in mobility or cognitive function, and social care services or other social amenities in urban areas than rural areas, which affects the elderly persons in the rural areas.⁹

Access to ICT: The urban areas witness more access to Information and Communication Technology (ICT) solutions than the residents of the rural areas. The use of technology to improve older people's access to recommended healthcare devices like BP monitoring machines, etc is being denied.

Social Amenities and Infrastructural Facilities: The poor supply of social amenities and infrastructural facilities in the rural areas trigger the massive out-migration of the rural residents which affect the care offered to older persons, which widows are mostly affected.

Poor Social Networks: This is attributed to risk of social isolation and feelings of loneliness because of difficulties in mobility and maintenance of social networks, whereby there would be free flow of communication with old persons in one community and other older residents.³⁰ Loneliness has been shown to affect not only mental but also physical well-being with significant links to poor cardiovascular health, cognitive decline, dementia and premature death.³³

Transportation and Mobility: Older people in rural areas experience more difficulties in accessing mobility and transportation services than those in the urban areas.

Other differences between the older persons in the urban areas and that of the rural areas are but not limited to the following; Informal care networks, affordable/suitable housing, basic infrastructure like pipe borne water, sewage, good telecommunication networks, pressures of overcrowding, financial grant or interest-free loans supports.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION OF FINDING

In this study, it was discovered that the ageing in human experiences impose innumerable challenges or problems. Some of the ills encounter by the senior citizens are economic problem or poverty; physiological problems, problems of elderly abuse, housing, ill-health and loneliness and isolation. The poor or lack of adequate attention given to the senior citizens in Nigeria attribute to development of various illnesses suffered by them such as dementia, parkinson, cancer, arthritis, stroke, kidney diseases, and the most suffered diabetics and hypertension. These observations lead to the intestate exit of these senior citizens. It was also observed that senior citizens centres can contribute immensely to the relief of these challenges and problems,if well equipped and implemented. Finally, it was discovered that poverty overrides other challenges of the elderly persons, as a result of inadequate funds to sustain oneself on feeding, clothing, housing, especially when one is sick.

CONCLUSION AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

Poverty is a threat which affects both the quality and length of lives, reduces the ability of families to adequately provide for senior citizens wellbeing, and is a significant cause of family breakdown and healthy imbalance in the homes. Social Protection and Assistance programmes on the elderly aim to reduce elder abuse, ill-health and poverty, as well act as a safety net for their general wellbeing. The Social protection systems which included social assistance, social insurance and labour market policies act as essential safety nets for poor and vulnerable citizens.

RECOMMENDATIONS

A piece of legislation to adequately cater for the need of the aged population is important, but even more important is the will to implement the right policies that benefit them. Some of the provisions of the bill actually do not require legislation before they can be implemented by the organs responsible for implementation including the various ministries of health as well as social and welfare ministries. Some of the provisions such as right to first consideration in queues and emergencies, reserved parking spaces, express lanes, and assistive service for all modes of transportation are social conventions. They mainly require social re-orientation to implement.

The three arms of government have their roles to play in protecting Nigeria's elderly. While the federal government can develop and implement a holistic policy in this regard, it is the government closest to the communities – the state and local governments – that can provide effective and practical care to the older population.

Despite the many economic challenges that the new administration of President Bola Ahmed Tinubu is faced with, attending to the needs of the elderly is important. This makes a consideration and passage of the Older Persons (Rights and Privileges) Bill by the 10th National Assembly as well as presidential assent quite imperative.

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